

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B330
Date: 4 December 2007
Take Off: 11:07:00
Landing: 16:32:09
Flight Time: 5h25m09

Campaign: ADIENT / TOFAMS

Operating Area: North Sea

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Cloud Physics / CCM2	Jim Crawford	FAAM
5	Flight Manager	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
6	Mission Scientist 1	Ben Johnson	Met Office
7	Mission scientist 2	Simon Osbourne	Met Office
8	CVI	Paul Barrett	Met Office
9	CVI	Jeff Norwood-Brown	Met Office
10	Wet Neph	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office
11	CPI	James Dorsey	Manchester
12	Dropsondes	Steve Devereau	FAAM
13			
14			
15			

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B330
 Date: 04 December 2007
 Project: RAINCLOUDS
 Location: Chilbolton and SW Approaches

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
105209		Start-Up	0.34 kft	123	52'04.36N 0'37.48W
105817		ASP	0.34 kft	064	Open
110700		T/O	0.33 kft	212	Cranfield
110700	111628	Profile 1	0.72 - 10.0 kft	212	start on t/o
111730		Video	10.0 kft	250	FFC1 DFC1
115018		Sonde 1	16.0 kft	250	q1005
115108	120919	Profile 2	16.0 - 0.09 kft	250	
120919	121012	Profile 3.1	0.09 - 0.54 kft	236	
121020	122017	Run 1	0.51 kft	221	500ft to 3500ft
122018	122325	Profile 3.2	0.50 - 3.5 kft	215	500ft to 3500ft
122338	122411	Profile 3.3	3.5 - 3.1 kft	214	
122557	123603	Run 2	3.0 kft	038	3000 ft below cloud base climb in turn
123603	123708	Profile 3.4	3.0 - 4.0 kft	027	climb in turn 3000ft to 4000ft
123745	124746	Run 3	4.0 kft	228	FL040
124746	124837	Profile 3.5	4.0 - 4.5 kft	232	FL040 FL45
124944	125946	Run 4	4.5 kft	041	FL45
125117		Video	4.5 kft	055	FFC2 DFC2
130124	131126	Run 4.2	4.5 kft	240	fl45 to fl55
131126	131246	Profile 3.6	4.7 - 5.5 kft	235	start run end
131340	132401	Run 5	5.5 kft	069	FL55 BBRs retracted late 13:21
132447	132749	Profile 4.1	5.2 - 2.5 kft	072	@132422
132749	133057	Profile 4.2	2.5 - 5.5 kft	115	FL25 - FL55
133058	133345	Profile 4.3	5.5 - 3.3 kft	118	FL25 - FL55
133346	133609	Profile 4.4	3.3 - 5.5 kft	126	FL55 to 3300ft
133724	134025	Profile 4.5	5.5 - 3.1 kft	121	
134055	134342	Profile 4.6	3.0 - 5.5 kft	119	
134524	134853	Profile 4.7	5.5 - 2.6 kft	120	q1010
134906	134941	Run 6	2.6 kft	097	
134941	135245	Profile 4.8	2.9 - 5.5 kft	096	
135246	135605	Profile 4.9	5.5 - 2.5 kft	056	q1014
135605	135849	Run 7.1	2.5 kft	072	
140214	140946	Run 7.2	2.5 kft	253	
140331		Overhead Chilbolton	2.5 kft	254	
141150	141648	Run 8.1	3.0 kft	063	
141635		Overhead Chilbolton	3.0 kft	070	
141947	142856	Run 8.2	3.0 kft	247	
142133		Overhead Chilbolton	3.0 kft	254	
142714		Video	3.0 kft	254	FFC3 DFC3
143133	144015	Run 9.1	3.5 kft	047	
144324	145128	Run 9.2	3.5 kft	240	
144452		Overhead Chilbolton	3.5 kft	254	
145340	145825	Run 10.1	4.0 kft	050	
150231	151027	Run 10.2	4.0 kft	240	
150440		Overhead Chilbolton	4.0 kft	256	
151148	151236	Run 11.1	4.5 - 5.4 kft	139	
151254		event	5.5 kft	077	avoidance
151416	151549	Run 11.1	4.5 kft	059	
151906	152749	Run 11.2	4.5 kft	243	
152759	153114	Run 11.3	4.5 kft	055	
153643	154833	Profile 5	4.5 - 16.0 kft	240	
154846		Sonde 2	16.0 kft	257	
163209		Land	0.37 kft	213	
163500		ASP	0.40 kft	355	closed
163820		End position	0.38 kft	308	52'04.36N 0'37.50W

B330 Track 04-DEC-07

RAINCLOUDS Sortie Brief: Stratocumulus measurements

Date : 4 Dec 2007

Flight Number : B330

Mission Scientist : S.Osborne / B.Johnson

Sortie Aims: The principal aim of this sortie is to obtain measurements of the microphysical, dynamical and radiative characteristics of stratocumulus cloud over sea areas around the UK. These will be combined with surface-based measurements at Cardington and Chilbolton to provide a comprehensive observational study of the evolution of a Sc layer over land. The combined dataset will be used to study the performance of the Unified Model.

Stacks of straight /level runs are flown to determine vertical profiles of turbulent fluxes and to document cloud microphysical structure. Sawtooth profile alongwind is used to study variations in cloud top and base heights, inversion properties and LWC profiles.

Sortie Location: Bristol Channel / SW Approaches and **either** over land in SW or Chilbolton depending on cloud conditions

Weather conditions: A layer of stratocumulus forming over the sea and extending over the land. An absence of medium / upper cloud is preferred but not essential. No precipitation falling into the Sc layer. Wind direction between about 225 and 280 degrees true.

Instrument requirements:

- JW / Nevzorov to be zeroed when in clear air at any altitude when straight / level.
- Cloud physics console. Normal operation of all probes
- Turbulence probe – monitor performance when in icing conditions.

Sortie detail:

1. Take-off Cranfield 1100z.
2. Transit to SW approaches at FL160 [40 min, T=40mins]
3. Drop sonde #1
4. Profile descent to 50ft, 1000ft/min [15mins, T=55mins]
5. Commence stack of SLRs of 10 min duration, Orientation either along- or acrosswind, as convenient. Minimum number of altitudes to be flown: 500ft asl, Cloudbase – 500ft, Cloudbase +500ft, mid-cloud-level, Cloudtop – 500ft, Cloudtop + 1000ft. [70mins, T=125 mins]
6. Commence sawtooth profile heading downwind. Max.altitude Cloudtop + 500ft, min altitude Cloudbase – 1000ft. Ascent / descent rate 1000ft/min [20min, T=145 mins].

Depending on cloud conditions either

Terminate the run in item 6 in a location where it is possible to commence 10 min straight / level legs over land.

7. Repeat item (5) over land [70min,T=215 mins]
8. Repeat item (6) in the reverse direction (heading back to sea). [20min,T=235 mins]

9. Repeat as much of item (5) as is possible within remaining time leaving time for final ascent and sonde in items 10/11. [35 min, T=270 mins]
10. Profile ascent to FL160 at 1000ft/min [15mins, T=285mins]
11. Drop sonde #2 [5mins, T=290mins]
12. Return transit to Cranfield [40mins, T= 330mins]
13. Land at Cranfield

OR

7. Profile ascent to FL160 at 1000ft/min [15mins, T=160mins]
8. Drop sonde #2 [5mins, T=165mins]
9. Reposition to the Chilbolton area to fly an inbound leg on the alongwind radial. [30 min, T=195 mins].
Note: Runs are only possible over Chilbolton if the cloud top is 500ft or more *above* the safety altitude (2300ft amsl).
10. Straight / level leg of 5 min oriented along a radial within ~10 deg of mean wind direction towards radar and finishing overhead the site. Procedure turn to reverse heading. Repeat the 5 min straight / level leg, commencing run start prior to passing outbound over the radar site. Procedure turn. [18 min, T = 215]
11. Flight patterns at 10. to be flown at altitudes: Cloudbase – 500ft, Cloudbase + 500ft, mid-cloud-layer, Cloudtop – 300ft. Altitudes also selected on advice from Radsearch (80min, T =295)
14. Profile ascent to FL160 at 1000ft/min [15mins, T=305mins]
15. Return transit to Cranfield [25mins, T= 330mins]
16. Land at Cranfield

Mission scientist debrief

B330 – RAIN CLOUDS / STRATOCUMULUS over ocean & Chilbolton

Location

Over the Bristol channel /SW approaches then work over Chilbolton.

Mission aims

Evolution of stratocumulus from ocean to land and comparison study with Chilbolton Cloudnet.

Weather

Large, fairly uniform warm sector over England and S. Ireland with WSW winds at 10-15Kt at surface and 30Kt at 5000ft. Overcast with boundary layer stratocumulus filling most of the warm sector. Some altocumulus and cirrus cloud in the morning over central-eastern parts of England associated with the warm front.

Flight plans

Take off 11Z from Cranfield. Profile ascent from take off through BL. Then transit at FL160 to Bristol channel. Drop a sonde over Bristol channel just before making descent. Descent to 50ft shows 7/8 of stratocumulus between 3500 and 5000ft. 1/8 bits of cloud around 500-1500ft at the top of a surface marine BL. Thermodynamics show a small hydrolapse and temperature inversion at 1,500ft and the main inversion at 5000ft. Significant aerosol observed from Neph ($50 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$) in the marine boundary layer (up to 1500ft). A stack of 6 SLRs performed going parallel to the wind: 500ft, 3000ft (500 below cloudbase), 4000ft (500 above cloud base), 4500ft x2 (500 below cloud top), 5500ft (500 above cloud top). A series of sawtooth profiles was performed whilst transiting from Bristol channel to Chilbolton via Devon. These were going between 5500 and minimum permitted altitude, which was 2500 or 3000. Most of these sawtooths went below cloud base. Cloud tops over land were same height as over ocean at approx 5000ft, occasionally a little lower at 4500ft. Cloud base was around 3000ft but occasionally higher at 3500ft. 1/8 of stratocumulus below the main deck at approximately 1000-2000ft. A series of 11 5-min runs over Chilbolton were made from 2500 to 4500 at 500ft intervals, 2 at each altitude, plus a third at 4500ft. Most of these runs were successful and included an overpass at Chilbolton but a couple of the in-bound runs were aborted and diverted away a few miles before reaching Chilbolton. However, a successful run and overpass, or near overpass was made at each of the altitudes. The radial approach of successful runs was 254 degrees. Drizzle was observed in the cloud quite frequently by 2DC 2DP and CVI.

Summary

A good flight for insitu sampling of stratocumulus over ocean and over Chilbolton.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.330** Date 4.12.07 Name Ben Johnson Page 1 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
110700 1108 ⁷⁰⁰	T10 P1		SW	Cranfield	Cloud base 750 Ft Profile started at T10
					multiple cloud layers of thin Sc 750 - 2000ft, 3500 - 4500 Alto cu also.
111628	P1 END P1	FL100	250		A little wisp of cloud about 9,500ft. Alto cu still above. No precip. Alto cu / cirrus clearing ahead Sc looks broken in places i.e. 718.
11125		FL160	265		Climbed up to FL160 for transit to Bristol channel
11140		FL160	265		CID 2 not available at the moment.
115018	SONDE 1	FL160	275		
115108	P2	FL160	275		Patchy Alto cumulus / cirrus clearing more as we go west. Sc look nice & homogeneous now. We have been over ocean for past 5 mins.
1155					SID2 back with us
1205					Cloud top at 5000ft
		Clouds			5000 - 4000 ft, then sudden bits of cloud at 500 or 1000 ft.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.330** Date **4/12/07** Name **Ben Johnson** Page **2** of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
120919	End P2	50 ft	250	Point A	
121020	Run P2	500 ft			
120919	P3-1	50-500 ft	215		Less are oriented along wind.
121020	R1	500 ft	215		
122018	P3-2	500-300	215		
122338	P3-3	3500 - 3000	215		Run at 3,000 ft = 500 ft below cloud base
122557	R2	3000	25		Cloud base is locally 500 ft lower out here than at other end of SLR stack
					CVI seeing a little bit of drizzle but cloud physics seeing no drizzle. Visually we are not seeing anything on windscreen.
123603	End R2	3000	25		
123603	P3-4	3-4 kft			
	R3	4000	215		
123708	End P3-4	4000			Run in-cloud (500 above cloud base)
123745	R3	4000	225		Intermittently in and out of cloud
					CVI giving increased concentration now $\sim 150 \text{ cm}^{-3}$
					Surface aerosol layer was only up to 1,500 ft in the surface MBL

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.30.3..** Date **4/22/07** Name **Ben Johnson** Page **4** of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					132447 - 134025
		5,500			
		2,500			
		3,300			
		3,000			
		2,500			
					Saw toothing cloud tops consistently at 5,000ft, cloud bases ~ 3,500ft or 3,000ft Scudgy clouds at ~1000ft
1335					Now over Devon
1340					Brizzle on windscreen
1356		2500			Run over Chilbolton at 2,500 NE direction
140331	R7	2500			Run over Chilbolton at 2,500 sw direction
	R7.2				
141635	R8	3000			Overpass Chilbolton. 500ft below
142133	R8.2	3000			Over pass Chilbolton? cloud base
	R9.1	3500			Got diverted away on inbound run to Chilbolton so approached it a 230°
	R9.1 3500				
1442	R9.1	3500			Overhead Chilbolton Cloud base is somewhere between 3000 and 3500 We are predominantly in cloud at 3500 This is our Cb + 500ft run.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B303** Date **4/12/07** Name **Ben Johnson** Page **5** of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
14452	R9.2	3500	254		Overhead Chilbolton
1449		3500			Out of cloud
		3500			Drizzle observed on windscreen and by ZDC.
145340	R10.1	4000			
145825	End	4000			Overhead Chilbolton
150251	R10.2				Overhead Chilbolton
1504	R10.2	4000			Overhead Chilbolton
1508	†				occasionally out of cloud even at 4,000ft
151148	R11-1	4,500			Run aborted just b4 overhead at Chilbolton due to ATC
151530		4,500			Being diverted all over the place. Trying to get another approach to Chilbolton.
1520					
1520		4,500			Skimming cloud top. Back into cloud again mostly in cloud at 4,500ft
					Coming back for a run into Chilbolton at 4,500ft (2 nd attempt)
1530					Drizzle observed by CVI & ZDP on 4,500 runs.
1535					
1535	2 nd				Attempt cut slightly short by 3 miles due to traffic

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 330

Date: 07/12/07 **Operator:** JC **DRS Time:** 08:05:00 **DAU1 Time:** +0 **DAU2 Time:** +0 **DAU3 Time:** +0 **Aux1 Time:** +0 **Aux2 Time:** +0 **Page 1 of 1**

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
Post -take off seadas, ffssp & sid1 & sid2 started 2dp ok 2dc ok pcasp vref = 8v sid1 ok sid2 locks up when program starts, after entry of flight number for file label. Computer has to be rebooted to recover. Ffssp signal base 14&2 Annulus base 2c&2f Threshold control 40998 Sig control 59200 & 55002 Annulus control 63370 & 50664																	
114500	0.5	0.04	169	0	-	0	0	0	0							Transit in clear air	
11 52 00 sid2 now ok																	
115108																Profile 2 started in clear air	
115811	1.7	0.05	170	0	0	0	0	0	0							Fl100, clear air : 2dp slightly noisy	
120304	7	0.09	181	3000	3000	5	0	8	0							Thin layer	
120645	20	0.08	248	10	1	0	0	100	0							Between layer & surface	
120930																50ft	
121018	50	0.09	253	200	10	0	0	0	0							Run 1 500ft	
121500	50	0.09	274	200	10	0	0	90	0								
122000	40	0.1	293	100	10	0	0	0	0								
122017																End run	
122150	7	0.08	304	3	0	0	0	0	0							2000ft	

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.6V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.5V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.3V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = n/a	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 0.9 CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -0.9V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = n/a	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = 12mW	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = -3.5V		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 330

Date: 07/12/07 **Operator:** JC **DRS Time:** 08:05:00 **DAU1 Time:** +0 **DAU2 Time:** +0 **DAU3 Time:** +0 **Aux1 Time:** +0 **Aux2 Time:** +0 **Page 2 of 2**

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
122600	8	0.08	334	3	0	0	0	0	0							Run 2 3000ft	
123100	14	0.08	334	3	0	0	0	0	0								
123600	14	0.08	335	10	0	0	0	0	0								
123803																End run 2	
123749	14	0.08	364	20	30	0	0	0	0								
124500	10	0.08	510	V	1000	0	0	0	0								
			124742 sid2 flagging error as not responding, still seems to be recording data.														
124800																End run 3	
125000	10	0.28	540	V	V	0	0	0	0							Run 4.1; 4500ft	
125150	80	0.3	569	2000		235	100	1000V								Entering cloud	
125500	385	0.3	689	3000		200	175	3000									
130000	160	0.3	963	3000	2000	24	0	450								End run 4.1	
130130	150	0.3	1114	3000		13	150	250								Start run 4.2; 4500ft	
130600	400	0.3	1349	3000	2000	535	200	891									
130800																Touching cloudtops	
131100	7	0.3	1447	1000	100	0	0	0	0								
131126																End run 4.2	
131330	3	0.07	1479	0	0	0	0	0	0							Start run 5.1	
131900	4	0.08	1479	0	0	0	0	0	0								
132300	7	0.08	1479	0	0	0	0	0	0								
122400																End run 5.1	
132500																Cloud penetration in profile 4.1	
133015																Cloud penetration in profile 4.2	
133150																Cloud penetration in profile 4.3	
133400																Cloud penetration in profile 4.4	
	200	0.3		3000	3000	59	200	1100									
	Typical readings during short cloud penetrations																
133800	650	0.3	2064	3000	3000	34	150	800								Cloud penetration in profile 4.5	

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.6V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.5V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.3V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = n/a	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 0.9 CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -0.9V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = n/a	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = 12mW	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = -3.5V		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 330

Date: 07/12/07 **Operator: JC** **DRS Time: 08:05:00** **DAU1 Time: +0** **DAU2 Time: +0** **DAU3 Time: +0** **Aux1 Time: +0** **Aux2 Time: +0** **Page 3 of 3**

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
134200	123	0.3	2471	3000	3000	21	150	250								Profile 4.6	
134700	165	0.3	2599	3000	3000	41	200	216								Profile 4.7	
135045	535	0.3	2791	3000	3000	156	250	2000								Profile 4.8	
135430	330	0.3	2983	3000	3000	54	300	2333								Profile 4.9	
135600	25	0.09	3038	10	1	0	0	V								Run 7.1	
135900																End run 7.1	
140222	38	0.08	3040	10	1	1	0	100								Run 7.2	
140946	18	0.1	3075	100	10	16	300	1300								End run 7.2	
141150	35	0.13	3082	100	10	45	225	16								Run 8.1	
141650	14	0.1	3104	100	10	18	350	666								End run 8.1	
141950	17	0.1	3110	30	10	14	325	2200								Run 8.2	
142858	30	0.1	3127	100	3	72	275	1816								End run 8.2	
143130	140	0.25	3299	2000	1000	177	350	791								Run 9.1	
144015	60	0.3	3601	3000	1000	30	225	250								End run 9.1	
144330	34	0.3	3845	3000	2000	17	225	60								Run 9.2	
145128	27	0.1	4031	V100-1000	V1-10	17	300	2000								End run 9.2	
145340	172	0.3	4220	1000	1000	250	300	1500								Run10.1	
145825	126	0.3	4463	2000	1000	9	200	40								End run 10.1	
150231	47	0.3	4857	2000	2000	7	200	33								Run 10.2	
151030	90	0.3	5302	3000	2000	28	175	583								End 10.2	
151148	564	0.3	5561	3000	2000	207	250	1900								Run 11.1	
151550	736	0.3	5655	3000	2000	617	175	758								Pop up to 5000ft	
151906	283	0.3	5917	3000	1000	711	225	333								Run 11.2	
112749	366	0.3	6280	3000	3000	23	350	850								End run 11.2	
152759	543	0.3	6855	3000	2000	194	125	600								Run 11.3	
153114	283	0.3	7223	3000	2000	32	150	558								End run 11.3	
153710	3	0.08	7793	0	0	0	0	90								Profile 5 clear air	
154200	1	0.05	7793	0	0	0	0	266								FI100	

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.6V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.5V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.3V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = n/a	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 0.9 CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -0.9V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = n/a	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = 12mW	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = -3.5V		

B330 CVI log

10/18/07 3:28:16 AM
 12/18/07 10:30:42 AM
 12/18/07 10:31:16 AM 10.30 powered up ok, set 1 control to 2.3
 12/18/07 10:31:22 AM 10.30 powered up ok, set 1 control to 2.3
 12/18/07 10:31:23 AM 10.30 powered up ok, set 1 control to 2.3
 12/18/07 10:31:29 AM 10.30 powered up ok, set 1 control to 2.3
 12/18/07 11:22:13 AM 10.30 powered up ok, set 1 control to 2.3
 12/18/07 11:22:15 AM 10.30 powered up ok, set 1 control to 2.3
 12/18/07 11:29:58 AM 10.30 powered up ok, set 1 control to 2.3
 12/18/07 11:30:06 AM 10.30 powered up ok, set 1 control to 2.3
 12/18/07 11:35:29 AM 11:35 set up for cvi mode
 12/18/07 11:41:03 AM EF off, Nopc=0.8, L=1.9 (+0.3=2.2)
 12/18/07 11:41:14 AM EF off, Nopc=0.8, L=1.9 (+0.3=2.2)
 12/18/07 11:51:30 AM 11:51:08 start of profile descent
 12/18/07 11:58:19 AM 1158: FL100
 12/18/07 12:03:48 PM 12:03 incloud
 12/18/07 12:05:21 PM cloud base12:05
 12/18/07 12:09:46 PM profile climb 12:09
 12/18/07 12:10:47 PM 12:10:20: run 1 500ft
 12/18/07 12:14:29 PM 12:11 cloud physics PCASP~50; CPC1.0, pcasp(cvi)~3
 12/18/07 12:15:14 PM 12:15 broken cloud, base
 12/18/07 12:18:08 PM cpc~3
 12/18/07 12:20:43 PM 12::20:17end of run start of profile 3.2
 12/18/07 12:20:56 PM cnc sample - flow rate =0.94
 12/18/07 12:23:40 PM cloud base ~3.5kft, descent back to 3kft for run
 12/18/07 12:26:20 PM 12:25:57run2 3kft just below cloud base
 12/18/07 12:26:35 PM altered flow rates just prior to run start
 12/18/07 12:27:11 PM cloud physics - no precip, cpi, small precip
 12/18/07 12:27:41 PM cnc sample=0.88
 12/18/07 12:31:40 PM cloud estimate 14kft thick (captain)
 12/18/07 12:34:06 PM T samp = 49.9 - too high?
 12/18/07 12:36:27 PM 12:36:03 end of run 2 start of profile climb 3.4
 12/18/07 12:36:36 PM 12:36:03 start of profile climb 3.4
 12/18/07 12:37:44 PM 12:37:08 end of profile climb 3.4 3kft-4kft
 12/18/07 12:38:44 PM 12:37:45 start run3 4kft skimming cloud base
 12/18/07 12:41:16 PM altered flow back to ~1.0
 12/18/07 12:41:54 PM 12:40 increase in PCASP reading, just below cnc
 12/18/07 12:44:33 PM occasional increase in PCASP to high vales - shattering
 of large precip (as reported by CPI)?
 12/18/07 12:44:53 PM t samp =36.2
 12/18/07 12:48:10 PM 12:47:46 end of run 3
 12/18/07 12:48:24 PM 12:47:46 start of profile 3.5
 12/18/07 12:49:34 PM 12:48:37 end of profile 3.5
 12/18/07 12:50:25 PM 12:49:44 run 4 4.5kft, cloud base
 12/18/07 12:51:30 PM 12:51 altered flow back to ~1
 12/18/07 12:51:56 PM 12:51:45 in cloud
 12/18/07 12:53:01 PM 12:52 OPC>CPC
 12/18/07 12:53:58 PM cloud physics - drizzle
 12/18/07 1:00:08 PM 12:59:46 end of run 4
 12/18/07 1:00:26 PM 12:59:46 start of run 4.1
 12/18/07 1:02:11 PM 13.01.24 start of run 4.2 alt=4.5kft in cloud
 12/18/07 1:03:19 PM sample flow ok sheath flow ok ref voltage ok
 12/18/07 1:06:33 PM particle sizes up to 2micron (channel 20)
 12/18/07 1:10:29 PM 13:10 time stamp on pcasp=02:45??
 12/18/07 1:12:13 PM 13:11:26 end run 4.2
 12/18/07 1:12:31 PM 13:11:26 start pro 3.6 4.5-5.5kft
 12/18/07 1:14:02 PM 13:13:40 start run5 5.5kft
 12/18/07 1:25:37 PM 13:24:22 start of sawtooth
 12/18/07 1:25:57 PM pcsasp size range mainly below channel 15, 0.8micron

12/18/07 1:27:03 PM 13:26 - shattering just before?
12/18/07 1:28:32 PM 13:27:29 end 4.1 2.5kft
12/18/07 1:28:53 PM 13:27:29 start 4.2 2.5kft
12/18/07 1:31:36 PM 13:30:57 end 4.2 5.5kft,
12/18/07 1:31:55 PM 13:30:57 start 4.3 5/5-3.3kft,
12/18/07 1:34:15 PM 13:33:45 end 4.3 3.3kft,
12/18/07 1:34:28 PM 13:33:45 start 4.4 3.3kft,
12/18/07 1:36:39 PM 13:36:09 end 4.4 5.5kft,
12/18/07 1:36:53 PM 13:36 ALTER L VALUE
12/18/07 1:37:26 PM L VALUE = 5.2, L indicator no reading 2.75
12/18/07 1:37:47 PM 13:37:24 pro 4.5 5.5kft-3kft
12/18/07 1:38:40 PM pcasp - prob showing lower conc. than previous pass thru
cloud
12/18/07 1:40:51 PM 13:40:25 end pro 4.5 not quite below
12/18/07 1:41:22 PM alter l contrl to 7.2 l indicator 3.75
12/18/07 1:41:32 PM 13:40:55 start pro 4.6 3kt
12/18/07 1:43:07 PM pcasp , similar size range - mainly up to chng5, lower
conc, under 10, ignore low channels (noise?)
12/18/07 1:44:07 PM 1:43:42 end pro 4.6 fl55
12/18/07 1:44:39 PM L control to 9.2 l indicator reading 4.63
12/18/07 1:44:47 PM above cloud
12/18/07 1:46:20 PM 13:45:24 start pro 4.7 fl55 down
12/18/07 1:47:10 PM pcasp in cloud reading not much at all
12/18/07 1:47:37 PM 1:47 l control to 8.2, l indicator to 4.25
12/18/07 1:47:51 PM pcasp higher conc, cpc
12/18/07 1:48:42 PM 148: below cloud l cont to 4.2 l ind to 2.26
12/18/07 1:49:20 PM 13:48 end pro 4.7 some broken cloud below
12/18/07 1:50:19 PM 13:49.06 run6
12/18/07 1:50:48 PM 13:49.41 end run 6
12/18/07 1:53:04 PM 13:49.41 start profile 4.8
12/18/07 1:53:21 PM 13:52:46 end profile 4.8
12/18/07 1:53:28 PM 13:52:46 start profile 4.9
12/18/07 1:54:12 PM l cont set to 2.2 l ind reading 1.27 at start of profile
4.9
12/18/07 1:56:26 PM 13:56:05 end profile 4.9
12/18/07 1:56:34 PM 13:56:05 start run 7
12/18/07 1:57:31 PM sample flow just over 1, sheath flow around 20, left as
is
12/18/07 1:59:27 PM 13:58:49 end run 7.1 overhead chilbolton
12/18/07 1:59:49 PM l - 3.2 L ind 1.85
12/18/07 2:03:10 PM 14:02:14 start run 7.2 2.5kft below cloud
12/18/07 2:03:45 PM 14:03:30 overhead chilbolton
12/18/07 2:04:12 PM 14:03:31 overhead chilbolton CORRECTION
12/18/07 2:07:09 PM
12/18/07 2:07:36 PM PROGRAM SHUT DOWN (accidental) restarted 14:07
12/18/07 2:07:46 PM l control reset to 3.2
12/18/07 2:08:00 PM new file name B330A
12/18/07 2:10:13 PM 14:09:46 END RUN
12/18/07 2:12:10 PM 14:11:15 start run 8.1 3kft
12/18/07 2:14:47 PM filters on? should now be bypassed
12/18/07 2:17:15 PM 14:16:48 end run 8.1
12/18/07 2:17:34 PM 14:16:35 overhead chilbolton
12/18/07 2:17:54 PM altered l cont=8.2 Lind=4.27
12/18/07 2:18:54 PM check flow: sample~1 sheath ~20
12/18/07 2:21:14 PM 14:19:47 start run 8.2 3kft
12/18/07 2:21:53 PM 14:21:33 overhead
12/18/07 2:22:13 PM Lind=4.27
12/18/07 2:29:19 PM 14:28:56 end run 8,2
12/18/07 2:31:01 PM cnc sample = 0.9
12/18/07 2:32:07 PM 14:31:33 start run 8.2 3.5kft
12/18/07 2:41:32 PM 14:40:09 end

12/18/07 2:41:39 PM 14:40:09 end 9.1
12/18/07 2:41:57 PM alter flow rates back to 20, 1
12/18/07 2:42:52 PM Lcont=5.2
12/18/07 2:42:59 PM Lcont=5.2
12/18/07 2:43:52 PM 14:43:24 start run 9.2 3.5kft
12/18/07 2:45:18 PM 14:44:52 overhead chilbolton
12/18/07 2:47:45 PM cnc sample = 0.88
12/18/07 2:48:48 PM sample flow to ~0.75 to be altered at end of run
12/18/07 2:51:57 PM 14:51:28 end run 9.2
12/18/07 2:52:33 PM Lcont to 3.2 Lind=1.82
12/18/07 2:53:18 PM Lcont to 3.2 Lind=1.82 sample flow adjusted to 1.0
12/18/07 2:54:09 PM 14:53:40 run 10.1 4kft
12/18/07 2:54:54 PM opc>cnc in places, liquid on windows
12/18/07 2:57:27 PM cnc sample still 0.87
12/18/07 2:57:58 PM sample flow to 1.25
12/18/07 2:58:56 PM 14:58:21 end run 10.1 overhead chilbolton maintain
heading
12/18/07 2:59:31 PM increase Lcont to 7.2, in same cloud looks homogenous,
Lind to 3.76
12/18/07 3:03:00 PM 15:02:31 start run 10.2 same settings
12/18/07 3:04:54 PM 15:04:06 overhead chilbolton
12/18/07 3:12:12 PM 15:10:27 end run 10.2 aktered Lcont to 4.2 Lind to 2.28
adjusted flows
12/18/07 3:14:41 PM 15:1148: start run 11.1at 4.5kft short run air traffic
12/18/07 3:14:50 PM interrupted
12/18/07 3:14:52 PM interrupted
12/18/07 3:14:53 PM interrupted
12/18/07 3:15:05 PM 15:114:16 recommence run 11.1
12/18/07 3:16:06 PM 15:15:48 end run 11.1
12/18/07 3:17:32 PM cnc flow 0.85
12/18/07 3:22:08 PM 15:19: start run
12/18/07 3:27:46 PM 15:27 start inbound run 4.5kft
12/18/07 3:27:47 PM 15:27 start inbound run 4.5kft
12/18/07 3:28:05 PM altered Lcont to 2.2 just after start of run, Lind=1.33
12/18/07 3:28:38 PM altered Lcont to 2.2 just after start of run, Lind=1.33
12/18/07 3:28:50 PM flows both ok , 1, 20
12/18/07 3:31:24 PM 15:31:15 end of run
12/18/07 3:37:08 PM 15:36:42 profile 5 to FL160
12/18/07 3:45:38 PM flow rate altered during climb
12/18/07 3:46:28 PM pcasp counting 27 particles/cc at 4206metres 15:46
12/18/07 3:47:03 PM cnc sample down to 0.59
12/18/07 3:48:44 PM 15:48:33 end of profile
12/18/07 3:49:24 PM 15:48:33 end of profile

Flight:

B330

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problems

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevezorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Report Created 21/12/2007
14:01:29

Misc Core

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Fax machine:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H:

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Last Updated:

05/12/2007 13:12:57

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP:

CIP 100:

CIP 25:

CPI:

CVI:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC 3025 (AMS):

INC:

VACC:

CPC 3010A (CVI):

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR:

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B330

Date: 4 December 2007

Instruments

1. CGPS pc u/s
2. PSAP not operated

Aircraft

Satcom-H Calls

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

^ Clipboard power button

Date: 04/12/07

Flight No: B 330

Pre-Flighter: Mo

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	X	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
Aircraft Cabin: Power-up				
2	✓	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	Core Chem Operator
3	✓	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	✓	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	✓	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	✓	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	✓	HORACE	Recording data	
8	✓	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	✓	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	✓	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	✓	Nevezorov	Checked and OFF	
12	✓	GPS	Checked	
13	✓	INU	Align	
14	✓	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	FFC scrolling, reset pwr, ok
15	✓	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	✓	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	Chem Operator
17	✓	FWVS	Set up & on AUTO	
18	✓	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	✓	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	✓	Heimann	Calibration Checked	No DLU signal
21	X	TWC	ON & Checked	JW + Heimann swapped on DLU!
22	✓	GE	Balance checked	No DLU Signal
23	✓	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	X	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	✓	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	
26	✓	CNC	Butanol filled	
27		Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	No comms to Neph

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
28		CGPS	Set up	
29	✓	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
External Checks				
30		Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
31		JW	Cleaned & Checked	
32		DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33		NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
34		Nevezorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
35		GE	Cleaned & Checked	
36		Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
37		Camera Windows	Cleaned	
38	✓	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
39	X	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	Not available (6 stars)
40		All other covers	Removed	
41	✓	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	N/A
42		Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
43		Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
44		Tools	Avalon informed	
Avalon Checks				
		Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		Signed
		ICEX applied		
		Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -	a) Nil b) 1/2 traps c) 1/4 full or more	
		Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B330:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
CPI	CPI operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	7 Jan 2008	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras
3 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Dr Jonathan P. Taylor

Manager Atmospheric Radiation Research Group
Met Office
Cordouan 2 W079
FitzRoy Road
Devon
EX1 3PB
UK

Tel: +44 (0)1392 884647
Fax: +44 (0)1392 885681

E-mail: jonathan.p.taylor@metoffice.gov.uk